

IMPROVEMENT IN MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITE BY COMPRESSIVE DEFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

The change in mechanical properties and microstructure brought about by compressive deformation were investigated for the Al_2O_3 and SiC particles reinforced 6061 aluminum matrix composites. The composite specimens prepared by the powder extruding method were subjected to compressive pre-straining at different temperatures. The compressed specimens were subsequently heat treated, and their tensile properties and microstructures were measured. The strength of the composite which reinforced with relatively large spherical Al_2O_3 particles are decreased by the compression at low temperature. But they are increased by the compression at higher temperatures. The strength of the composite which reinforced with angular SiC particles were not decreased and increased even in compression at room temperature. Such decrease and increase in strength properties brought about by compressive deformation can be explained by the negative effect due to the cavity formations at the interfaces of particle/matrix and the positive effects of improvement in interface bonding, densification of matrix powder alloy and increment of dislocation density in the matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Particle reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) which have high specific stiffness and strength and good wear resistance are very useful to realize lightweight structural parts. However the MMCs have not been much put to practical use in the automobile or machine industries, though some trial products have been made in various fields. The MMCs, especially aluminum matrix composites, can be easily fabricated by either liquid phase methods like melt stirring, rheocasting, compocasting and spray deposition methods, or solid phase methods like powder extruding, hot pressing and HIP processes. However the development of an economical secondary processing for complex shape products is very important to apply them much more to the mass-products. Machining processes are difficult for the MMCs because of their hard reinforcements. Direct cast in complex shape after compocasting or melt stirring processes can be employed, although the viscosity of the melt is increased with increasing reinforcement content and a lot of porosities may be generated.

An alternative process to produce near net shaped components of MMCs is to employ the deformation processing like forging of MMCs billets, because the MMCs can be deformed like conventional metals at not only elevated but also room temperatures. When the deformation processing is employed as the secondary processing, there are advantages in being able to use the existing forming techniques without large modifications and in some enhancements of properties by the microstructural improvement like grain refinement, work hardening and texture strengthening of the matrix alloy. From the above viewpoint the authors are now focusing on the secondary deformation processing of particle reinforced aluminum matrix composites. The upsettability of the composites [1-3], their flow stresses at large strain [4-6] and the changes in microstructure and properties by the plastic deformation [7-10] have been studied experimentally and theoretically.

The MMC consists of ductile matrix metal, hard particles and their interfaces, and will be subjected to various loading during the deformation processing. Therefore the internal stress and strain distributions would be much complicated as compared with conventional metals and the complicated internal stress state would give rise to microstructural degradations. Failure in the MMC is believed to be due to the cavity formations at the particle/matrix interfaces or by the particle cracking. Whitehouse and Clyne [11,12] reported that stable voids can exist before failure in the composite subjected to tensile straining and the nucleation of voids does not lead immediately to failure of the material. The authors [7,8] also observed by the in-situ tensile test in a scanning electron microscope that debonding of the interfaces and particle fractures are occurred in low tensile strain but they do not propagate with increasing strain. The cavity formation during plastic straining before failure would influence mechanical properties of the deformed composites. Lloyd [13] reported that the Young's modulus of SiC/6061 aluminum composite is reduced by plastic straining and that the reduction is owing to particle damage during straining. Mochida et al [14] followed the phenomena by an analytical model which can explain the particle failure mode observed in the experiment. The authors also reported that the strength of forged SiC/6061 aluminum composite is reduced as compared with that before forging [3] and that the decrease in strength property of Al₂O₃/6061 composite deformed in tension is due to microstructural degradation during tensile deformation [10].

The above mentioned positive effects brought about by deformation processing on mechanical properties of deformed composites would compete with the negative effect of such cavity formations. Although the negative effect would exceed the positive one in the deformation of tensile stress field, the improvement in the properties would be expected in compressive stress field. In the present work the change in mechanical properties and microstructure brought about by compressive deformation at various temperatures are investigated and their relationship are discussed for the particle reinforced aluminum matrix composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

MATERIALS

Two kinds of aluminum matrix composites were prepared with a powder extruding method in order to get good dispersion of particles and to prevent some complicated chemical reactions between the matrix and particles. The matrix aluminum is an air atomized A6061 alloy powder with mean diameter of around 40 μm , whose composition is shown in Table 1. The A6061 alloy has good deformability and can be strengthened by the subsequent heat treatment. The used reinforcements are spherical Al₂O₃ (mean diameter : 25 μm) and angular SiC (mean diameter : 14 μm) particles, and their volume fractions are both 10%. The relatively large mean diameter of

Table 1. Composition of A6061 aluminum alloy powder.

Mg	Si	Fe	Cu	Cr	Zn	Mn	Ti	Al
1.11	0.60	0.42	0.34	0.19	0.01	0.01	-	bal.

Figure 1. Micrographs of prepared composites.

the reinforcements was employed for easy observation of the microstructural changes.

The matrix aluminum alloy powder and the reinforcement particles were mixed by use of a V-type mixer. The mixed powder was directly extruded at 773K in the sheet of 15x2mm. The micrographs of as extruded composites are shown in Fig. 1, which both consist of well dispersed particles in the matrix.

PRE-STRAINING

The extruded composite sheets are cut in length of 60 mm and processed in T4 heat treatment, that is water quenching after solid solution treatment at 793K for 2 hours, to improve its deformability for subsequent compressive pre-straining.

Four sheet specimens are compressed together in width direction under restricting in thickness as shown in Fig.2, namely plane strain compression, in various compressive strains at room and elevated temperatures. The compressed specimens are machined in tensile specimens shown in Fig.2 and processed in T6 heat treatment, that is water quenching after solid solution treatment at 793K for 2 hours followed by aging at 448K for 8 hours. Then the tensile test is carried out to measure strength and ductility

Figure 2. Method of compressive pre-strain and tensile test. (Unit: mm)

Figure 3. Proof stress and tensile strength of compressed Al₂O₃/6061 composite.

The surfaces of some specimens were polished before pre-straining to observe the change in microstructure. Inner microstructures of compressed specimens were also observed by removing matrix alloy near surface by electrolytic polishing. Fracture surfaces are also observed after tensile tests.

RESULT

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Fig. 3 show the proof stress and tensile strength of the Al₂O₃/6061 composites which are compressed at different temperatures and processed in subsequent T6 heat treatment. In the previous work [10] it was found that the strength of the composite are decreased with tensile pre-strain at room, 573K and 773K temperatures. In the case of compressive pre-strain at lower temperature than 573K, the proof stress and tensile strength are also decreased as in tensile pre-strain, though they are slightly increased at lower strain than 10%. The decrement is less than that in tensile pre-strain and saturated at the strain of about 40%. The behavior is hardly dependent on the pre-straining temperature. On the contrary they are increased at every pre-strains by compression at higher temperature than 673K. The increment is slightly larger at 773K than 673K and also saturated at the strain of about 30%. The uniform elongation is hardly changed at every pre-straining temperatures.

Fig. 4 show the proof stress and tensile strength of the SiC/6061 composites which are pre-strained in compression and processed in subsequent T6 heat treatment. The proof stress and tensile strength are not decreased with compressive pre-strain at every temperatures unlike the Al₂O₃/6061 composites. They are increased in pre-straining at room and 573K temperatures but hardly changed at 773K. The effect of pre-straining temperatures on them is contrary to that in the Al₂O₃/6061 composites. The uniform elongation is hardly changed at every pre-straining temperatures as well as the case of Al₂O₃ particles.

MICROSTRUCTURE

In the compressive pre-straining at room, 473K and 573K temperatures, some cavities at inter-

Figure 4. Proof stress and tensile strength of compressed SiC/6061 composite.

faces can be observed as shown in Fig. 5 not only on the surface but also inside of the both composites specimens. They are less and smaller than those observed in the specimens pre-strained in tension, and few cavities owing to particle fractures can be seen. When the composite is subjected to the compressive stress, the matrix alloy is elongated in normal to the compressive direction. Then the matrix at both sides of the particle flows far from the particle, and the cavity is occurred at the interface. But the cavity is not enlarged with increasing compressive strain, because it is upset by the compressive deformation of the matrix. In the present experiment the angular elongated particles are oriented perpendicular to the compressive axis, because they were oriented parallel to the extruding direction. Then the cavities by interface debonding in the SiC/6061 composites are occurred at edged ends of the angular particles and they are smaller than that in the Al₂O₃/6061 composites.

On the other hand only a few small cavities can be seen in the composites compressed at 673K and 773K. Fig. 6 shows the matrix flow observed on the surface of the specimens compressed at high temperatures. Because the flow stress of the matrix is very low and its ductility is very high at high temperature, the matrix alloy can flow along the shape of the particle. Therefore the cavities will be hardly occurred at the interfaces.

Figure 5. Cavities observed in compressed composites.

Figure 6. Micrographs on the surface of compressed composites.

DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties of deformed composites are influenced by complicated microstructural changes brought about by deformation processing. The main negative effect is cavity formation during deformation processing. The cavity formations are due to debonding of interfaces between matrix/particles and particle fractures. Especially the cavities occurred at lower strain are mainly due to the interface debonding and they are depend on the bonding strength of interfaces. The bonding strength of the Al₂O₃/Al composites is generally weaker than that of SiC/Al ones, because of poor wettability and reactivity between Al₂O₃ and aluminum alloy. Fig. 7(a) shows the Al₂O₃ particle observed in the fracture surface of the tensile specimen of as extruded composite, namely without pre-compression. Although some dimples of matrix aluminum alloy to prove ductile fracture can be seen on the surface of the particle, a part of original surface of the particle can be also seen on it. It means the debonding at the interface is occurred owing to a part of incomplete bonding between the particle and matrix during extrusion.

The size and number of the cavities brought about by deformation are depend on the size, shape and volume fraction of the particles and the stress state like tension or compression. In general large cavities would be occurred in tensile deformation. But those observed in the Al₂O₃/6061

Figure 7. Al₂O₃ particles in fracture surfaces of as extruded and compressed composites.

composites used in the present work are comparatively large in spite of compressive deformation, because the particles are spherical and relatively large. This negative effect would be large in pre-compression at lower temperature. Those cavity formations would induce the decrease in the strength property of deformed composites, because of decrease in capacity transporting external load from matrix to particles.

There are some possible positive effects, improve in interface bonding, densification of matrix powder alloy, increment of dislocation density and so on. In the compression at high temperatures the matrix alloy can flow along the shape of the particles as shown in Fig. 6. It could be predicted that the matrix alloy is strongly shared on the surfaces of the particles. Fig. 7(b) shows the Al_2O_3 particle observed in the fracture surface of the tensile specimen of the composite compressed at 773K. No part of original particle surface but many small dimples of the matrix alloy can be seen almost all over the particle surface. It would prove that the incompletely bonded interfaces in the as-fabricated composite could be improved and their bonding strength could be increased. This effect would be considerable in compression at higher temperature. The improvement in interface bonding would induce the increase in the strength property of deformed composites, because of the increase in capacity transporting external load.

Fig. 8 shows relative appearance density of $Al_2O_3/6061$ composites compressed at 573K and 773K. The relative density of the powder extruded composite is not 100%. The density is not decreased but slightly increased by compressive deformation in spite of some cavity formations. It would mean that the matrix powder alloy is not completely densified during powder extrusion and becomes denser in compressive deformation. It would result in the improvement of matrix property, but compete with the decrease in density by cavity formations.

The plastic deformation induces many dislocations in matrix alloy and results in strain hardening of the matrix. Especially much more dislocations are punched out around particles even at small plastic strain, because of mismatch in deformability of matrix and particles. It results in formation of subgrains and grain refinement of the matrix alloy. Of course such strain induced dislocations and hardening are considerable in the deformation at low temperature. The macroscopic strain hardening would be disappeared in post deformation heat treatment, solid solution treatment in the present work. However the dislocations around the particles would be not completely disappeared because of restriction by the particles. As the result the refinement of grains and precipitations in the matrix alloy and the improvement of the mechanical property are possible after post deformation heat treatment.

The densification of the matrix and the strain induced dislocations would result in the increase in the strength property of deformed composites owing to the increase in that of matrix alloy. Those positive effects can compete with the negative ones, and it results in the complex change in mechanical properties of deformation precessed composites. Relatively large cavities were formed in the $Al_2O_3/6061$ composite used in the present work in the compression at low temperatures. Therefore the negative effect by the cavity formations would exceed the possible positive effects, then the strength properties were decreased. On the contrary the negative effect would be little in the compression at high temperature, because only a few and small cavities were occurred. Therefore the positive effects, especially the improvement in interface bonding and the densification of the matrix would exceed the little negative one, then it resulted in the increase in

Figure 8. Relative density of compressed $Al_2O_3/6061$ composite.

the strength properties of deformed composites.

The negative effect would be not so much in the SiC/6061 composites, because the cavities formed by compression are very small as above mentioned even in compression at room temperature. The improvement in interface bonding would be also not so effective in the composite, because the sharing deformation would not so hard around the small and angular shape SiC particles. Therefore the positive effects owing to the densification of the matrix and the strain induced dislocations would exceed the negative effect by the cavity formations. Then the strength properties of deformed SiC/6061 composites were not decreased, but rather increased especially in compression at low temperatures.

CONCLUSION

The change in mechanical properties and microstructure brought about by compressive deformation at various temperatures were investigated and their relationship was discussed for the Al₂O₃ and SiC particles reinforced 6061 aluminum alloy matrix composites.

The proof stress and tensile strength of the composite which reinforced with relatively large spherical Al₂O₃ particles are decreased by compressive deformation at lower temperature than 573K. The decrease is due to the cavity formations at the interfaces of particle/matrix during compressive deformation. On the contrary few cavity formations can be occurred in the compression at higher temperatures, and the strength properties are increased due to the improvement in interface bonding and densification of matrix powder alloy. The strength properties of the composite which reinforced with angular SiC particles are not decreased but increased even in compression at room temperature in spite of a few cavity formations. The increase in mechanical properties of the composite would be mainly due to that the positive effects of densification of matrix powder alloy and increment of dislocation density in the matrix by the compressive deformation would exceed the negative effect of the cavity formations.

REFERENCES

1. N. Kanetake, N. Nakamura and S. Terada, *J. Japan Inst. Light Metals*, **40**, 271, (1990).
2. N. Kanetake, *Advanced Technology of Plasticity 1990*, Japan Society for Technology of Plasticity, **1**, 53, (1990).
3. N. Kanetake, T. Choh and M. Ozaki, *Sci. and Eng. of Light Metals*, Japan Inst. Light Metals, **513**, (1991).
4. N. Kanetake and H. Ohira, *J. Mater. Pro. Tech.*, **24**, 281, (1990).
5. N. Kanetake and N. Nakamura, *J. Japan Soc. Technology of Plasticity*, **31**, 536, (1990).
6. N. Kanetake, M. Ozaki and T. Choh, *J. Japan Soc. Technology of Plasticity*, **34**, 1332, (1993).
7. N. Kanetake, T. Choh and M. Nomura, *Proc. 2nd Japan Int. SAMPE Symposium*, 778, (1991).
8. N. Kanetake and T. Choh, *Proc. 3rd Int. SAMPE Metals Conf.*, M414, (1992).
9. N. Kanetake and T. Choh, *Proc. 9th Int. Conf. Composite Materials*, 634, (1993).
10. N. Kanetake, H. Saiki and T. Choh, *Proc. 39th Int. SAMPE SAMPE Symposium*, 1741, (1994).
11. A. F. Whitehouse and T. W. Clyne: *Composites*, **24**, 256, (1993).
12. A. F. Whitehouse and T. W. Clyne: *Acta. metall. mater.*, **41**, 1701, (1993).
13. D. J. Lloyd, *Acta metall. mater.*, **39**, 59, (1991).
14. T. Mochida, M. Taya and D. J. Lloyd, *Mater. Trans. JIM*, **32**, 931(1991).